

A Moonlit Brazilian Metropolis

Guanabara Energy Mast (GEM)

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Abstract: Any Wasted anthropogenic heat sinks accumulate in Earth's bioshell, threatening destabilization of macroenvironmental (climatogenic transformation) biophysical global ecosystems and causing problems for people. Due to population growth, urbanization, and industrialization, Rio de Janeiro's heat island effect will potentially become more pronounced than is apparent today. Solar-power generated microwave beams, originating from the Moon, sent to a few strategic ground stations served by Earth-orbiting specialized microwave beaming satellites, ultimately can replace some combustion energy generation infrastructures worldwide. Moon-Earth companions have potential to become a coupled celestial body economy. For Brazil, that means present day smokestack generators can be mothballed, held in reserve during unanticipated itinerant Moon-Earth beaming disruptions (which may occur for a variety of reasons). In the interim, Brazil's hydropower infrastructure will continue to provide dominant baseload electricity for its flourishing cities. Proposed here is an innovative inflated tower-ground station or "power park", which is generically referred to as the Guanabara Energy Mast (GEM). Placed on a single partially sacrificed Paquetá Archipelago island, GEM could theoretically provide electrical power for the entire Guanabara Bay urbanized shoreline.

Keywords: Solar-power, Moon, Guanabara Bay, GEM (Guanabara Energy Mast), macroproject, microwave beaming satellites, urban electricity supply.

Resumo: Qualquer desperdício de calor antropogênico se acumula na biosfera da Terra, ameaçando desestabilizar os ecossistemas biofísicos globais (transformação climatogênica), e causando problemas para as pessoas. Devido ao crescimento populacional, à urbanização e à industrialização, o efeito de ilha de calor no Rio de Janeiro poderá se tornar mais pronunciado do que é hoje. Feixes de micro-ondas gerados por energia solar, originários da Lua e enviados para algumas estações terrestres estratégicas atendidas por satélites especializados em transmissão de micro-ondas em órbita da Terra podem, em última análise, substituir parte da infraestrutura de geração de energia por combustão em todo o mundo. A interação entre a Lua e a Terra tem o potencial de se tornar uma economia acoplada entre os corpos celestes. Para o Brasil, isso significa que as atuais usinas termelétricas podem ser desativadas, mantidas em reserva para eventuais interrupções na transmissão de energia entre a Lua e a Terra (que podem ocorrer por diversos motivos). Enquanto isso, a infraestrutura hidrelétrica brasileira continuará a fornecer a principal fonte de energia de base para suas cidades em expansão. Propõe-se aqui uma inovadora estação de energia em forma de torre inflável, ou "parque energético", genericamente denominada Mastro de Energia da Guanabara (MEG). Instalada em uma ilha parcialmente sacrificada do Arquipélago de Paquetá, a MEG poderia, teoricamente, fornecer energia elétrica para toda a orla urbanizada da Baía de Guanabara.

Palavras-chave: Energia solar, Lua, Baía de Guanabara, MEG (Mastro de Energia da Guanabara), macroprojeto, satélites de transmissão de micro-ondas, fornecimento de eletricidade urbana.

1. Introduction

The term “Weather” is a contranym that can simultaneously refer to both biophysical erosions, even to the point of eradication or disappearance, as well as infer successful endurance of a violent Earth-atmosphere storm. It should be noted that words effectively foster or hinder communication about potential future anthropogenic landscapes. That is, they drive conceptual transformations of landscapes as well as facilitating solutions to recognized land and sea-surface human property-use problems. Although Rio de Janeiro’s well-known favelas exist in sunlit squalor, some Space Age landscape planners anticipate potential 21st Century construction of favela-like lunar bases for their so-called modernized Solar System! Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, hosted the UN Conference on Environment and Development (1992) as well as the wildfire-plagued Belem-centered UN Conference of the Parties to the Framework Convention on Climate Change (2025). While some researchers, mostly in other large ecosystem countries, perceive advanced lifestyles on the Moon, the 14th International Architecture Biennial of Sao Paulo (2025) offered reminders that peoples’ immediate future remains within the Earth-bioshell. Under present-day conditions, humans attempt to live during a period of proven, faulty, misconstrued, or demonstrably false international information saturation. This fact-obfuscating ideological entrenchment is amply reflected by simplistic, even evasive, fuzzy wordage of popular “globalized environmental news” rhetoric.

Climate regime change of Earth ecoregions is not a simple global air pollution problem that can be regulated by international, national, and local taxation. Capricious postural decrees issued by deceived or misinformed politicians, to the educated indicate that the diversity of a large segment of the Earth-bioshell cannot be stabilized by a policed exclusionary walling of the Amazon River Basin. Uniformed authoritative temporal instructions issued by politicized governing bodies headquartered in the tropical riverside town of Belem ($1^{\circ} 26' 59''$ by $48^{\circ} 28' 0''$) run the risk that the enclosed Indigenous Amazonian people [1], ultimately, might object to the imposition of a non-commonsensical academic “Ecology” that morphs into an objectionable population-specific survivalist “Eke-ology” [2]. With an estimated AD 2025 population of ~16 million, Rio de Janeiro State produces ~11% of Brazil’s misconstrued GDP [3].

Viewed from an inhabited or automated outer space Earth orbit satellite, shaped like an incandescent lightbulb, Guanabara Bay has the potential to host a moonshot macro-engineering engagement that totally revamps the 133 km-long embayment shoreline’s electricity-powered infrastructure. Brazil outlawed all use of incandescent bulbs in June 2016. The macro-imagined GEM is partly air-inflated but possibly would include some slight use of helium and hydrogen gases. The microwave receiver GEM megaproject we outline here was devised many years ago by Alexander A. Bolonkin (1933-2020) but has been temporally stalled until this propitious moment when it appears that all needed essential infrastructural systems are “A-OK” to “GO” [4] (**Figure 1**). Societal acceptance of our proposed partially air-inflated Guanabara Energy Mast (GEM) will be influenced by accumulating technical knowledge as well as the embedded symbolic and historical meanings tied to local Brazilians’ experience as well as generational national trends of publicly expressed thought about controversial energy provision infrastructures. To forestall public and political rejection, however, we deliberately refuse NASA’s definition of “technical lands”, a branding designation that implies a simple functional role with relative indifference to the GEM’s rectenna architectural visibility and public acceptability [5]. Hence our choice of the GEM acronym. A singular inexpensive-to-build A. A. Bolonkin inflated mast, situated on one or more of the Paquetá Archipelago islands within Guanabara Bay, represents in its basic architectural outline the vertical electricity supply wires that terminate in the filament of (a nowadays Brazil-banned) incandescent lamp glass globe which glows brightly because of Joule heating.

GEM can become an imposing new landmark for prideful Guanabara Bay communities, visually complementing Niteroi’s famous futuristic sightseeing overlook, but not a spacearium, the flying saucer-shaped Museu de Arte Contemporânea de Niteroi [6]. (Niteroi, is the international conference site for the

World Symposium on Artificial Intelligence for Climate Change Adaptation and Mitigation, 7-8 May 2026, held at Federal Fluminense University.) GEM, along with the museum, could provide additional advertisable place-branding for Brazil's 384 km² Guanabara Bay. This noteworthy infrastructure could recharacterize human responses to contemporary regional climate changes which include hydrological variability that increasingly compromises hydroelectric energy security. Development of GEM would avoid transferring one of the region's biggest assets into a looming economic liability. Such an adverse turn of events could be reminiscent of the unglamorous difficulties Rio de Janeiro experienced in its months-long AD 1963 brownouts, blackouts, power rationing, factory shutdowns, and overall high monetary costs for feeble public and private electricity services [7-8].

Feasibility planning for GEM involves the formulation of a public policy panoply comprised of feasible, acceptable, and implementable urban and rural infrastructures serving all people in Rio de Janeiro State. GEM, and its closely associated cable and wireless distributive infrastructures, will co-optimize Brazil's vital ecosystem-country investment in the steady primary source lunar microwave beam generation. Uninterrupted microwave transmission from a singular geostationary Earth-satellite [9] and/or quasi-geostationary Earth-satellite [10], of low-cost microwaved power derived from the Moon power generation and transmission facility to the Rio de Janeiro-servicing Guanabara Energy Mast has obvious advantages.

Unfolded from their carrier rocket payload containers during orbit installation, such relay satellites may have the 2-leaf clover-leaf shape of a double paddle [11] that can, with stimulation of human visualization, be imaginatively comprehended as Earth-orbiting "sky butterflies" such as *Parides Ascanius*, Rio de Janeiro's beautiful Fluminense swallowtail butterfly. On 22 May 2023, transmission of power from orbit was successfully done using the Microwave Array for Power-transfer Low-orbit Experiment, a first experimental package of the Space Solar Power Demonstrator. The transmitted power was ~200 milliwatts received at the ground station on the campus of the California Institute of Technology in Pasadena, California, USA. Commercialization is being undertaken by, for example, Virtus Solis Technologies (founded 2019; GOTO: *virtussolis.space*) as well as others. It is noteworthy that Virtus Solis has designed the world's first space-based power energy system that is able to directly compete with all forms of energy.

Whenever operating, an Equator-shadowing geostationary and/or quasi-geostationary microwave beam relay Earth-satellite could relay power to Rio de Janeiro State's GEM situated within Guanabara Bay. The ground distance separating the Equator from Paquetá Archipelago is ~2,489 km. Because the height of the orbiting microwave satellite collector above the Equator is 35,873 km, a direct focused microwave beam broadcast from outer space less than one degree latitude north of Belem (Brazil) is ~35,959 km long. With the satellite's failsafe, real-time adjustable beam-aimer actively maintained at 3.969⁰ and the ground-station microwave receiver, the geographically North-facing rectenna installed inside Guanabara Bay, can be tilted at an angle of ~86.03⁰. (By contrast, common ground-displayed photovoltaic panels at Rio de Janeiro must be optimally slanted ~30⁰.)

Consequently, DC power derived from the GEM can be widely distributed to all Guanabara Bay shoreline and islandic communities by overhead/underground/submarine transmission cables and/or simply broadcast generally through air! Note that NASA broadcast power has achieved an AD 2025 distance test record of ~1.5 km. Wireless mobility is prompted by expressed customer desires for wire-free power supply to allow the widespread use of cellular telephones, laptop computers, various household appliances as well as public and private transport systems. Line-of-sight favelas could capture collimated GEM unfocused general and aimed power with community or individual antennas whilst topographically shielded reverse hill-slope favelas will require either hill-crest relay towers or electricity powerlines connected to localized transformers owing to a distinct service districting organization [12]. In industrial chemical facilities, by exciting specific elements in target materials, microwave beams can focus transformational heat where it

is needed, improving existing chemical synthesis and reducing the use of non-renewable combusted energy sources to do laboratory and factory chemical processes [13].

Figure 1. Brazil's second most populous metropolitan region, imaged during nighttime on 4 July 2022 AD. Some illuminated vessels, perhaps a few reflecting incidental moonbeams, cause a coruscation of boat lights atop the bay's vast pacific seawater expanse. The continuous lit straight-line traversing Guanabara Bay near the dredged entrance channel is a commuter-used box girder road bridge first opened to traffic in AD 1974, Ponte Presidente Costa e Silva, that links Rio de Janeiro and Niteroi, Brazil. Paquetá Archipelago, excluded by the image's frame, is located to the upper right-hand and, thus, is unimaged here. (Image: International Space Station, iss067e176807.)

2. Earthwork: 22° 45' 20.99" South Latitude by 43° 06' 19.20" West Longitude

During Spring 2023, 7-9 November, through late Summer (March 2024), citizens of Rio de Janeiro, even those then resident or working in Guanabara Bay's most picturesque Paquetá Archipelago (**Figure 2.** referenced in the Section Title above), endured a heatwave with high daily maximum air temperatures exceeding 43° C. At ~5-8° C higher than usual, this was the most intolerable hot weather episode in 63 years! Imagine, as the artist Siah Armanjani (1939-2020) did with his hypothetical 32.1860 km-high/3.2187 km-diameter artwork *North Dakota Tower* (1968), Dr. A.A. Bolonkin's partially air-inflatable GEM, were it materialized, would fleetingly and consecutively shade sectors of Guanabara Bay from dawn to dusk as a very tall localized sundial! Resembling some magnificent tall limbless tree, but surely not a serendipitous landscape feature unseen from afar, it nevertheless would be attractive to awe-struck wanderers, sober fun-seekers, and international tourists]14].

Figure 2. Oblique aerial image of the two main islands composing the Paquetá Archipelago. A.A. Bolonkin's partly air-inflated tower, an airspace-penetrating columnar GEM 1-3 km tall depending on technical requirements of the energy and distribution system, would have a 1,964 m² foundational ground footprint, a base with a 25 m radius. Though narrower and far taller, it would resemble London's 180 m-tall office-building, *The Gherkin* (aka, 30 St. Mary Axe). A corporate Public Art installation? GEM's inclined bowl-shaped rectenna will allow greater interception of microwaves than a flat one. The main island's area is ~1.2 km², full-time home to ~3,600 rural people, and GEM requires only 0.164% of the large island's entire pedestrian and EV-only subaerial geomorphic surface. The undredged strait between the two islands shown is ~100 m wide and shallow (Google Images.)

Usually, for residents and tourists, it is a pleasant, nearly 15 km one-way boat trip to Paquetá Archipelago's main island from the Rio de Janeiro downtown waterfront. This world-class city is seemingly constantly racked by many immediate civilian macro-problems but with remarkably weak governmental deployment of the urban region's many economic resources to cope with those obvious public disorder situations in a comprehensive manner [15]. The islands feature low-elevation hill terrain relief without the mainland's bulbous high-elevation mountainous Fucoidal gneiss lithic peaks of Sugar Loaf and the Corcovado, both <1 km in elevation.

GEM's ground base, its Operational Center, can demonstrate aesthetically planned facadism, namely by creating a cluster of artful boulder-like buildings, some even with walkable rooftop lookouts and perches that have the appreciable unadorned appearance of natural landscape objects [16]. GEM's realization requires shutdown of large commercial airports with necessary airliner approaches over Guanabara Bay which results in a spacious flat landscape opened for new 21st Century electrized housing and industrial developments! Perhaps large helicopters, VTOL aircraft can be substituted or all airports replaced with multiple Drone Aerodromes servicing only Guanabara Bay citizens? Guanabara Bay shoreline populations will have to decide about a consensual geographical outlook that includes decisions on (I) closeness to extant urban electrical tie-points and most essential load centers; (II) safety of GEM from seasonal torrential

rainfall and damaging lightning strikes; (III) GEM microwave beam spillover that creates a localized rectenna-caused unnaturally increased aerial heat-island effect; (IV) GEM Operation Center site security. Beam spillover from GEM's 100-200 m-diameter rectenna that impacts seawater is inconsequential because placid seawater reflects microwaves almost like a mirror, the showered energy penetrating <2.5 m.) Workers at GEM might wear specialized protective clothing such as eyeglasses, helmets, and uniforms with layered shielding fabric threads to prevent operator metabolic dehydration.

One of GEM's most significant electricity-users could be Dr. Nilo Serpa's proposed South Atlantic Ocean seawater electric pump macro-project. His speculated *Organum Hydraulicum*, intended to cost-effectively consume power as it artificially enhances by voluminous seawater supplementation the natural oceanic tidal flushing of Guanabara Bay's vital uppermost swampy region, especially near the Guapimirim reserved mangrove groves located a few kilometers east of Paquetá Archipelago [17-18]. Earth's massive world-ocean seawater tides are caused, in part, by the orbital nearness and Solar System movements of its Solar System primary, the Sun, and the Moon!

3. Ask for the Moon, not Utopia!

Some Brazilian politicians and celebrities, having access to radio and television microphones, speechify that weather can provide all the ecosystem-country's electricity via weather-dependent solar photovoltaics and windmills [19-20]. As a result of the power of the microphones, large expenditures of taxpayer's monies are being committed to subsidize power-associated industries that are surprisingly reliant on natural weather conditions! Beyond that pun, we wonder, seriously, if such voices have background music, possibly "Windmills of Your Mind" (1969) composed by Michel Legrand, with lyrics penned by Alan and Marilyn Bergman seeping into their brains.

Since Rio de Janeiro and Niteroi are seaports, we view with horror the prospect of battery-fueled ships sinking in Guanabara Bay. The windmill industry requires the presence of bathymetric and other survey ships, offshore wind-turbine installation vessels equipped with on-board cranes, undersea cable layers, and offshore oil-platform crew transfer vessels. Shipwrecks will happen and we worry about spillage of acid and other toxic chemicals into the seawater that will be much worse than past Guanabara Bay petrochemical refinery oil pipe leakages [21]. Guanabara Bay's petrochemical factory, operational since 1961 AD, covers 13 km² and manufactures smog-inducing products such as gasoline, lubricants, diesel fuel, aviation kerosene, liquified natural gas, bunker oil, and naphtha. Smog resulting from local usage is distributed throughout Guanabara Bay by frequent breezes blowing south-southeast to north-northwest.

Oddly, one aspect of the pro-windmills trend that is markedly unpromoted by Brazilian legislators, corporations, construction union bosses and obviously benefiting Rio de Janeiro State and local governmental agencies is related to the numerous projects and proposals for floating or affixed wind-power farms is aesthetics. Owing to planet-Earth's curvature, the linear mechanical generator farms >4-5 km from land will be invisible to shoreline visitors. Floating offshore windmills must be securely anchored in locations where the wind is consistent and strong, operations will change the aerial environment significantly. Examples: (I) windmills can kill flying seabirds; (II) the soundscape created by constantly humming windmill machinery carries far downwind, then heard by annoyed recreational boaters, artisanal fisher-folk at work and acoustically-sensitive beachgoers; (III) windmills released from their deep-water anchorages by South Atlantic Ocean wintertime storms and unpredictable tsunamis may not sink but, instead, drift shoreward, posing a harmful pollution threat to Rio de Janeiro State beaches as ugly contaminating wreckage awaiting landfill or dumping at sea disposal. There is another aspect that windmill aficionados have left unclarified: windmills, located on landscapes or seascapes, are known to meteorologically change air's flow and even the presence or absence of iconic coastal fog and marine

stratocumulus cloud formations [22], remedied, in part, by Eduardo Kac-devised artworks. In other words, institutionalized societal “addictions” like windmills reinforce unsustainable behaviors [23-24]!

Lastly, imagine an amusing (or possibly alarming) feasible propaganda scenario: elected legislators, dutiful policy-makers, rapacious corporations, and bureaucratic public service announcements that currently hire all available kinds of advertising media might wish to add floating billboards. Ships have blessed names, so why not monumental billboards lauding living and deceased politicians and other noteworthy citizens? Rio de Janeiro in AD 1996 funded a floating Christmas tree, the “Árvore do Rio” anchored on an inland lake, the Lagoa Rodrigo de Freitas, which separates Ipanema from Jardim Botânico. More horrific still, since high-altitude aerial drones and Earth-orbiting satellites can image and live-televisé the seawater surface at night, there is at least a potential that clustered windmills will be decorated with lights which warn aircraft pilots as well as ship captains, but can be computer-programmed to illuminate synchronized flash advertisements: How about “Vote for X”? Or, if the South Atlantic windmill farm arrangement were markedly linear, an enormous flashing “arrow” pointing to a particular tourist trap or political hotspot? It is worth noting that Brazil made its final debt payment for the gigantic Itaipú Dam hydropower installation on February 2023 AD. Presumably, tax monies were liberated for other Brazilian infrastructure investments. The Brazil-Moon Power Program would take, at least 20-30 years to achieve working functionality.

During September 2024 wildfires in the Amazon River Basin blanketed 60% of South America, including Sao Paulo [25], with low-altitude haze and deteriorated air quality for several months afterwards [26]. “The emerging darkening of the... [Northern Hemisphere] ...relative to the... [Southern Hemisphere] ...is associated with changes in hemispheric differences in aerosol-radiation interactions, surface albedo, and water vapor changes” [27]. Clouds of all kinds play a vital role in the Earth-bioshell’s energy balance by regulating air temperature, distributing moisture, and influencing weather. That is the only reason that massive injections of particulate sulphate into high-altitude air is being considered, unwisely we think, by modern-day macro-engineers hoping to slow the planet’s recently recorded air warming due to all known natural and anthropogenic causes [28]. Above the von Karman Line, the low-Earth orbit satellite mass is accumulating fast, becoming a satellite collision menace as well as literally shading the Earth-bioshell from energizing natural sunbeams [29-30]. During November 2025, Star Catcher Industries, Inc. tested its wireless optical power transmission by delivering 11 kW of electrical power using a laser beam between two ground sites located at NASA’s Kennedy Space Center. Although tightly focused, in its working final configuration (that is, outer space to Earth-surface), optical beams have the same air-heating effect as sunshine (so-called incident stellar flux) and are visible! Think directionally inverted anti-aircraft searchlights as well as heyday Hollywood’s famed premier movie first screening celebratory Klieg lights. In other words, such different types of 21st Century infrastructure have uncharacterized hazards and thus people who will be most exposed remains a health concern.

4. Moonworks

Currently, Programa Espacial Brasileiro has a minimal spaceflight program which does not envision much future Brazilian effort expended on the surface of the Earth’s satellite, the Moon [31-32]. Guanabara Bay’s infrastructural imaginaries, which are settlement-shared outlooks of potentially realizable local infrastructure that are collectively clutched and either publicly enacted or resisted, include the prospect of mechanically duplicating indoors the best weather outdoors because of an expected hotter urban heat island effect [33]. Rio de Janeiro’s heat island results from its concentration of buildings, vehicular and metabolic heat emissions. Introduction of electricity sent from the Moon as microwave energy by GEM locally creates the potential for revenue cogeneration (*e.g.*, seawater desalination, frugal favela district heating schemes, even gaseous carbon dioxide direct capture) [34]. GEM could allow Rio de Janeiro some strategic independence from all international electricity transmission imports, serving as an essential transfer place

to other locales, even other continents [35-36]. Indeed, decommissions of windmills may become possible, restoring the beauty of the countryside and beach zones totally [37]. Beaming microwaves from one or more Earth-orbiting satellites to Paquetá Archipelago's GEM seems to be more beneficial for a stable regional weather regime than mirrored extra sunlight (during daytime or nighttime) or eye-endangering laser beams projected from outer space-sited commercial industrial facilities. Technology to securely control such satellites has become possible since the successful testing of quantum communication uplinks/downlinks [38].

All kinds of installations sited on the Moon have been proposed, and many kinds of technical devices have already been landed in working order on the surface of Earth's major natural satellite, in fact so many gadgets that, along with Mars, the Moon may be appreciated in super-futuristic historian chronicles to have an Anthropocene geological period in progress [39]. The Moon's regolith is malleable by robotic material movers and can efficiently be processed into many needed objects and devices useful in transforming the Moon into a significant part of Brazil's national GDP [40].

From the Earth, humans view the Moon's trajectory across the sky (horizon to horizon), always observing the near-side face (never the far-side face), always the same eye-seen crater and canyon topographic features. During ancient times, some people assumed the Moon's landscape mirrored Earth's [41]! From the Moon, lunar visitor human beings and their imagining machines perceive the Earth in the same place in the sky, day after day, but always rotating on its axis, revealing new features as the hours elapse. The optimal microwave beam is 12 cm in wavelength, ~2.5 GHz. Unlike sunlight, microwaves of such wavelength pass through clouds, rain, fog, and particulate aerosols with little absorption, approximately with the impact of ~20% noontime sunshine. This minimal absorption results in less direct anthropogenic bioshell air-heating than from reflected solar energy or laser beams. A decade after humankind first set foot on the Moon, David R. Criswell (1941-2019) pioneered the idea of utilizing the Moon as a solar energy gatherer for customers on Earth. His idea has been taken further by the Japan-based Shimizu Corporation [42].

5. The ingenious energetic matrix

Anthropogenic heat islands in large urban centers undermine people's quality of life, creating impactful climatic imbalances that affect ecological diversity. Large volumes of concrete are erected without any compensating native vegetation cover, forcing the migration of birds and consequently increasing the incidence of pests by disrupting the predator-prey chain. Simultaneously, misguided initiatives for capturing solar thermal energy — large areas covered by photovoltaic panels without underlying water channels for natural cooling — harm rural areas, creating the same negative consequences. In parallel to our proposed GEM macro-project, if Brazil had an effective space policy, we could boldly and innovatively consider implementing a small geostationary prototype grid of a few thermal collector satellites (inheriting some of the idea of a discontinuous Dyson sphere, although it is known that complete Dyson spheres are, in principle, unstable¹), capturing heat reflected from Earth and the moon, or directly from the Sun, supporting a highly economical energy conversion-transmission network. With this, we would have space itself as a natural refrigerator.

Particularly with respect to our proposed GEM macro-project, and complementing Bolonkin's initial ideas, it is possible to apply microwave metamaterials to control electromagnetic microwaves at will, from

¹ Apparently, due to this perceived instability, Freeman Dyson would have preferred not to have his name associated with this technology, although he formalized it. In reality, as Dyson honestly acknowledges, the idea was proposed much earlier by Olaf Stapledon, his friend and science fiction writer, in his beautiful 1937 novel "Star Maker". (Authors' note).

MHz to 100 GHz. As artificial flexible designs of meta-atoms at subwavelength scales, metamaterials make it possible to achieve medium parameters, such as refractive index and permeability, at extreme values not existing in nature (zero and even negative). As noted earlier, in the 2.5 GHz band, the opacity of the medium is easily overcome. At the current level of interdisciplinarity we have reached among the various specializations of materials science, GEM can also work in conjunction with another developing technology of great interest in the field of solar energy based on the sensitization of photovoltaic cells by quantum dots. Quantum dots (QDs) are nanoscale semiconductors whose nanostructures (shape and size) determine potential wells that confine electrons in discrete energy states, adding greater efficiency to ordinary cells (for more details, please see reference [44]). Operating as a complementary device to the GEM, a floating structure of photovoltaic cells sensitized by quantum dots would provide, on Guanabara Bay, sufficient auxiliary power to cover extraordinary operational and storage needs.

In short, large cities are dissipative systems where entropy accelerates considerably due to anthropogenic activities and interactions with their surroundings. Importantly, the modernist arrogance in urban planning is the main cause of urban climate imbalance, directly resulting from a futurism devoid of social awareness. The geophysical configuration of Rio de Janeiro inspires and favors the implementation of a sustainable, high-tech energy matrix. Brazil possesses a wealth of natural mineral resources to implement a robust materials and components industry; it is a matter of wanting to do it.

6. Summary

Brazil's below grade territory is a *cone* shape while its above grade national property is a *column* shape [43], the very shape of our proposed GEM macro-project for Guanabara Bay's Paquetá Archipelago islands. Airspace is generically understood as the column of air above a territory or land area. GEM offers a very large useful imported power level, the only limiting factor appears to be stray microwaves. While there are enormous, but incrementable, upfront investments needed to materialize GEM, there seem to be, overall, perceptible downward long-term monetary costs in terms of ever-progressing technology development and marketing. The risks of undertaking GEM seem doable, especially if done over a period of 20-30 years. Guanabara Bay can be restored to a cleaner condition, and all favelas can be powered at affordable costs.

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